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Legal Protection of Children Forced to Work Becoming a Public Figure According to Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 on Child Protection

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Abstract

The rapid progress of information and communication technology can have a negative impact on children's development. The existence of child artists is often seen as developing interests and talents, being popular, having more financial resources, and living in prosperity. This is more a form of economic exploitation carried out by their parents when the activities of the child artist ignore their human rights as a child. The research aims to examine legal protection and law enforcement against perpetrators who force children to work as public figures. This research uses a type of normative juridical research, namely examining in depth the principles of law, statutory regulations, jurisprudence, and opinions of legal experts and comprehensively looking at the law. The legal sources used are primary law and secondary law, namely using a statutory approach or books, articles, and journals. The research results show that legal protection for children is an effort to protect children's rights from acts of discrimination and exploitation in any form to ensure children's survival and normal growth and development, both physically, mentally, and socially; Law enforcement is a bridge effort to provide firmness to perpetrators who cause trouble or discriminate against children in any way. Law enforcement seeks to provide sanctions against someone who commits acts of exploitation of children through statutory regulations.

Keywords:

Legal Protection, Public Figures, Exploitation, Children.

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INTRODUCTION

A child is every human being under the age of eight years, Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection defines a child as someone who is not yet 18 (eighteen) years old, including children in the womb.

The value of children which is then used as a universal norm is that children are also seen as complete human beings, who therefore have human rights that must be protected. This view demands that adults (biological parents, government, and society) must take full responsibility for every child born into the world because it is part of the implementation of human rights (Supeno, 2010). Parents are obliged and responsible to care for, maintain, educate, and protect children, and develop children according to their abilities, talents, and interests. The government has inventoried children in an administrative structure in the form of records and is also obliged to provide basic education for a minimum of 9 (nine) years for all children (Muladi, 2005).

Nowadays, many children act as actors on social media which influences its popularity which is increasing day by day due to public interest. It is not uncommon to find children of public figures from birth to teenagers who have entered the world of entertainment, advertising models, children's magazine models, playing soap operas, starring in films, and having their own YouTube channel, so content is created by their parents and uploaded to social media.

The existence of child artists is often seen as developing interests and talents, being popular, having more financial resources, and living in prosperity. It is more a form of economic exploitation carried out by their parents when the activities of the child artist ignore their human rights as a child. Working beyond the specified time limit, and busy on and off air schedules, so that children do not have time to study, miss school, do not have time to play with peers, are violations of children's rights which are protected by law.

Children must be protected from negligence, violence, and exploitation. It must not be made the subject of commerce. Children must not work before a certain age, they must not be involved in work that is detrimental to their health or education, or which can affect the development of their body, soul, and morals. Every child has the right to receive protection from all possibilities that will interfere with the child's growth and development (Saudi, 2023).

Legal protection against child exploitation according to Law Number 35 of 2014 Article 66 states that special protection for children who are exploited economically and/or sexually as intended in Article 59 Paragraph (2) letter d is through: (a) dissemination related to protection of children who are economically and/or sexually exploited; (b) monitoring, reporting and providing sanctions; and (c) involvement of various companies, trade unions, non-governmental organizations and the community in eliminating economic and/or sexual exploitation of children.

The problems that arise are how is the legal protection for children who are forced to work as public figures? And how is the law enforced against perpetrators who force children to work as public figures?

The research aims to examine legal protection and law enforcement against perpetrators who force children to work as public figures.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Definition of Rights and Obligations of Children

The definition of a child varies according to applicable regulations, here are several definitions of a child, namely: (1) According to Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection states that a child is someone who has not reached the age of 18 (eighteen) years and includes children still in the womb; (2) Based on Article 330 of the Civil Code, in civil terms a child is someone who is considered immature if they have not reached the age of 21 (twenty-one) years or are not married. Based on the law that regulates child welfare, essentially states and stipulates that children under 21 (twenty-one) years of age are considered immature; (3) Based on Law Number 11 of 2012 concerning the Criminal Justice System, children in the criminal system are referred to as children aged between 12 (twelve) to 18 (eighteen). Based on the provisions in the International Convention regarding the rights of children, it states and stipulates that a child is someone who is not yet 18 (eighteen) years old; (4) Based on Article 1 point 4 of Law Number 4 of 1979 concerning Child Welfare which regulates children's rights, it states and determines that a child is someone who is not yet 18 (eighteen) years old unless there is a regulation from a country that can make them mature. The child is before the internationally agreed age requirement, and (5) based on the Law on Human Rights which states that a person who is not yet 18 (eighteen) years old or is unmarried and whose child is still in the womb is considered to be the definition of a child.

Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection states that the rights and obligations of children are stated in articles 1, 9, 14, 15 and 16, namely:

- (1) Children's rights are part of human rights that must be guaranteed, protected, and fulfilled by parents, families, communities, the state, government and local governments.
- (2) Every child has the right to receive educational education in the context of his personal development and level of intelligence by his interests and talents.
- (3) Every child has the right to be raised by his or her parents unless there are valid reasons and/or legal regulations indicating that separation is in the best interests of the child, which is the final consideration. In the event of separation as intended in paragraph (1), the child still has the right to: (a) meet directly and have regular personal contact with both parents; (b) receive care, maintenance, education, and protection to process growth and development from both parents by their abilities, talents and interests; (c) obtain living expenses from both parents; and (d) obtain other children's rights.
- (4) Every child has the right to receive protection from abuse in political activities, involvement in armed conflict, involvement in social unrest, involvement in events containing elements of violence, involvement in war and sexual crimes.
- (5) children are obliged to receive protection from torture, abuse, and inhumane punishments, children are also obliged to obtain freedom.

2.2. Legal Protection

Legal protection is an effort to protect the government or authorities with several existing regulations. In short, legal protection is a function of the law itself, namely providing protection. According to Satjipto Raharjo (2006) [4] legal protection is protecting human rights that are harmed by other people and this protection is given to the community so that they can enjoy all the rights granted by law, and according to Hadjo (1987) that legal protection is the protection of honor and dignity, as well as recognition of human rights possessed by legal subjects based on legal provisions against arbitrariness.

Several main aspects of the concept of legal protection: namely (1) justice and equality: this concept emphasizes the importance of providing fair and equal treatment to all individuals, without discrimination or discrimination. Regardless of social background, race, religion, gender, or other status; (2) human rights: the concept of legal protection involves the recognition and protection of every individual's human rights. This includes civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights that are inherent in every human being and must be respected and protected by law; (3) legal certainty: this concept requires the existence of laws that are clear, reliable, and can be understood by everyone. Legal certainty creates stability and justice in society because everyone knows what is expected of them and how the law will be applied; (4) Independence of Law Enforcement Institutions: Law enforcement institutions must operate independently and free from political or other party interference. This independence guarantees objectivity and fairness in law enforcement; (5) proportionality: this concept emphasizes that law enforcement must be carried out proportionally to the level of violations that occur. The sanctions or actions taken must be balanced with the violations committed, to prevent oppression or unreasonable sanctions; (6) community participation: legal protection requires active participation from the community in supporting efforts to protect their rights and interests. The community must play an active role in reporting violations, supporting the implementation of the law, and contributing to creating a just and safe environment; (7) institutional support and law enforcement: legal protection requires strong and trustworthy institutions to carry out law enforcement functions. Institutions such as the police, judiciary, and judiciary must be supported and provided with adequate resources to carry out their duties effectively; and (8) law as the highest authority: this emphasizes that law must be the force that regulates and controls government and society, not the other way around. The law is the highest authority that must be respected and followed by all citizens, including government authority and positions

(<https://fahum.umsu.ac.id/perlindungan-hukum-indonesia-pengertian-aspek-unsur-dan-contoh/>.)

2.3. Legal Protection of Children

The formation of the Child Protection Law was based on considerations as a juridical basis for implementing the obligations and responsibilities of parents, families, communities, government, and the state to protect children. In Article 74 of Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection, it is emphasized that to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of child protection, with this Law an independent Indonesian Child

Protection Commission was established. Therefore, by the mandate of Article 74 of the Child Protection Law, Presidential Decree Number 77 of 2003 concerning the Indonesian Child Protection Commission was issued, and finally, the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) was formed. Article 76 of the Child Protection Law, it states that: the Indonesian Child Protection Commission's duties are: (1) to socialize all provisions of laws and regulations relating to child protection, collect data and information, receive public complaints, carry out studies, monitor and evaluate, and supervision of the implementation of child protection; and (2) provide reports, suggestions, input and considerations to the President in the context of child protection.

The function of KPAI consists of 9 (nine) main areas, namely: (1) Social and Children in Emergency Situations; (2) Family and Care Sector; (3) Civil Rights and Participation; (4) Religion and Culture Sector; (5) Education Sector; (6) Health and Drugs Sector; (7) Pornography and Cybercrime; (8) Children in Conflict with the Law (ABH); and (9) Trafficking and Exploitation Sector.

Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection Article 1 Point 1 states that child protection is all activities to guarantee and protect children and their rights so that they can live, grow, develop, and participate, optimally by human dignity, as well as receiving protection from violence and discrimination.

Peter Newel, in his book "Talking Children Seriously: A Proposal for Children's Rights Commissioner" mentions several reasons why children need to be protected (Aqsa and Isnur, 2012), namely: (1) the costs of carrying out recovery as a result of failure to provide child protection is very high; (2) children have a direct and long-term influence on the actions/actions or lack of action/actions of the government or other groups; (3) children always experience gaps in service delivery; (4) children do not have voting rights, and do not have lobbying power to influence government policy; (5) children in many situations cannot access protection and fulfill their rights; and (6) children are more at risk of exploitation and abuse.

The form of child protection in Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection is: (1) Article 13 paragraph 1 states that as long as the child is in the care of parents, guardians, or any other party who responsible for caregiving, entitled to protection from violence, abuse, neglect and discrimination and injustice; (2) Article 15 states that every child has the right to receive protection from abuse in political activities, involvement involving elements of violence and involvement in war; and (3) Article 16 states that children are obliged to receive protection from torture, ill-treatment and inhumane punishment, children are also obliged to obtain freedom, and arrest and detention of children can be carried out as long as it is by the law.

2.4. Understanding Public Figures

A public figure or what is called a public figure is someone whose life will always be for public consumption. According to Widyatmoko (2011), a public figure is an individual who is known to the wider community, both because of his profession and competence. Furthermore, Praktikto (2007) stated that there are 3 criteria for evaluating a public figure,

namely: (1) Credibility, namely the trust given or highlighted by a public figure to the public. These can be words containing promises or the like; (2) Power is the strength or power that a public figure possesses and displays. This is something that is respected or looked up to by society; (3) Attractiveness, namely the attractiveness possessed by certain public figures, usually possessed by artists or celebrities, in terms of the physical or charisma possessed by the public figure. In physical terms, it can be seen from the appearance, good looks, character, and others that are inherent in the public figure.

Child public figures refer to children or teenagers who are famous or widely known to society, often through media, entertainment, sports, or other achievements. Children who become public figures have special rights and greater legal protection compared to adults because they are considered vulnerable to exploitation and the negative impacts of the public spotlight.

Forms of protection for young public figures, namely: legal protection, proper parenting, work restrictions, and education and welfare.

The positive impact on children who become public figures is that children who become public figures can get the opportunity to achieve success more quickly, have access to extensive experience and networks, and have the opportunity to inspire others, while the negative impact is that these children are vulnerable to psychological distress resulting from high expectations, invasion of privacy, and risk of exploitation or abuse. And risks to social and emotional development if they do not receive appropriate support.

2.5. Legal protection for public figures

Legal protection for public figures in Indonesia is not specifically regulated in one law that specializes in them, but several laws protect their rights, both relating to privacy, reputation, and protection from exploitation and defamation. Good, and other rights that may harm them.

Several statutory provisions related to the legal protection of public figures, namely:

- (1) Protection from defamation (Criminal Code and ITE Law)
 - a. The Criminal Code (KUHP), especially Article 310321, regulates defamation, both through oral and written statements. This defamation applies to anyone, including public figures.
 - b. Law Number 19 of 2016 concerning Amendments to Law Number 11 of 2008 concerning Electronic Information and Transactions protects public figures in terms of disseminating detrimental information through electronic media, such as social media.
- (2) Protection from exploitation (Law 35 of 2014 concerning Child Protection) Article 59, guarantees that children must not be excessively exploited in any way that has the potential to damage their physical and mental development.
- (3) Protection from violence and discrimination (Law Number 39 of 1999 concerning Human Rights)
 - a. Article 4 in human rights law guarantees that everyone has the right to protection from actions that harm their dignity and rights.

- b. If public figures, whether adults or children, experience violence or discrimination due to their status as public figures, they have the right to obtain legal protection.
- (4) Protection of Rights to Names and Images (Law Number 19 of 2002 concerning Copyright) Public figures also have rights to their image or identity which can be protected legally. This includes the right to protect their name from unauthorized use or unauthorized exploitation for commercial purposes. Copyright Law provides a legal basis for public figures to control the use of their names and images in media, advertising, or other commercial products.
- (5) Legal Protection through Law Number 19 of 2016 concerning Amendments to Law Number 11 of 2008 concerning Electronic Information and Transactions. The ITE Law protects public figures from spreading fake news or hate speech that could damage their reputation. Article 27 of the ITE law regulates the prohibition of spreading negative content through electronic media that can harm individuals, including public figures. Defamation through electronic media can be subject to criminal sanctions.

2.6. Child Labor

Children who do any type of work that has a nature or intensity that can disrupt education, and endanger their safety, health, and growth and development can be classified as child labor. Child labor is work that deprives children of their childhood, potential, and dignity, thereby harming their physical and mental development. Work refers to something that is physically, mentally, socially, or morally dangerous, and endangers children, as well as disrupting their schooling. It is declared a child worker if it meets the following indicators: (1) the child works every day; (2) exploited children; (3) children work long hours; and (4) school time is interrupted/no school.

Decree of the Minister of Manpower and Transmigration Number: Kep. 115/MEN/VII/2004 concerning Protection for Children Who Do Work to Develop Talents and Interests Article 3 paragraphs (1) and (2), namely:

- (1) Involving children in work to develop talents and interests must take into account the best interests of the child.
- (2) The best interests of the child as intended in paragraph (1) are carried out by, among others: (a) the child's opinion is heard and respected; (b) children are treated without hampering optimal physical, mental, intellectual and social growth and development; (c) children continue to receive education; (d) children are treated equally and without coercion.

2.7. Child Exploitation

According to Waluyadi (2009) in his book entitled "Child Protection Law" states that exploitation is an action with or without the victim's consent that is not limited to prostitution, forced labor or servitude, slavery, or practices similar to slavery, oppression, blackmail, physical, sexual exploitation, reproductive organs, or unlawfully moving or transplanting organs and/or body tissue, or exploiting a person's energy or abilities by another party to gain a good advantage.

There are various types of exploitation, namely (1) exploitation of natural resources, (2) exploitation of humans, (3) sexual exploitation, and (4) economic exploitation.

The impact of exploitation itself can leave deep wounds on the individuals who are victims. There are several impacts of exploitation, namely:

- (1) Psychological impacts such as trauma, depression, and anxiety often haunt them for a long period. Trauma resulting from exploitation itself can disrupt a person's psychological and emotional development, even into adulthood.
- (2) The physical impact on individuals who are victims of exploitation is also very serious. Victims of exploitation often experience health problems due to poor working conditions, physical violence, or lack of access to health services.
- (3) The social impact is no less detrimental to the victim. They often experience social isolation, stigma, and discrimination.

According to Supeno (2010), child exploitation is an effort carried out by a person or group of people to exploit or exploit other people's labor for mutual or personal interests.

Child exploitation is a person's arbitrary actions and discriminatory treatment of children carried out by the community or family to force the child to do something without paying attention to the child's rights such as physical and mental development.

Article 13 paragraph (1) letter b of the Child Protection Law states that exploitation includes actions aimed at using, exploiting, or blackmailing children for personal, family, or group gain. In general, there are two forms of exploitation of children, namely: sexual exploitation and economic exploitation.

In the Child Protection Law Article 66 states that what is meant by "economically exploited" is an act without the child's consent which includes prostitution, forced labor or services, slavery, oppression, blackmail, and use of physical/sexual reproductive organs for transfer or transplantation by a party. Others for material gain.

The definition of the worst forms of child labor according to Law Number 1 of 2000 concerning the ILO Convention in Indonesia generally includes children who are exploited physically and economically, which include, among other things: (1) children who are prostituted; (2) children who work in mining; children working as pearl divers; (3) children working in the construction sector; (4) children working on jermals; (5) children who work as garbage collectors; (6) children involved in production and activities that use explosives; (7) children working on the street; (8) children who work as domestic servants; (9) children working on plantations; (10) children who work in home industries; (11) children who work in home industries; (12) children working in aviation, processing and transporting wood; and (13) children who work in industries and types of activities that use dangerous chemicals.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a type of normative juridical research, namely examining in depth the principles of law, statutory regulations, jurisprudence, and opinions of legal experts and comprehensively looking at the law.

The legal sources used are primary law and secondary law, namely using a statutory approach or books, articles, and journals. The techniques for collecting the data taken are

documentation studies, which collect or manage data via the internet, and literature studies, which obtain information containing concepts, theories, books, and information related to the problem being studied.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Legal Protection for Children Who Are Forced to Work as Public Figures

Legal protection and rights for children is one side of the approach to protecting Indonesian children. So that the protection of children's rights can be carried out regularly, orderly, and responsibly, legal regulations are needed that are in line with the development of Indonesian society which is fully imbued with Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution (Sutejo, 2006). In Article 1 paragraph (2) of Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection, it is explained that child protection is all activities to guarantee and protect children and their rights so that they can live, grow, and develop, as well as, participate optimally by human dignity, and receive protection from violence and discrimination.

In Article 9 paragraph (1) of Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection which states that every child has the right to receive education and teaching in the context of personal development and their level of intelligence by their interests and talents.

According to Gultom (2008), [11] child protection can also be interpreted as all efforts aimed at preventing, rehabilitating, and empowering children who experience acts of child abuse, exploitation, and neglect, to ensure the survival growth, and development of children. Naturally, physically, mentally, and socially.

Children who become public figures are at great risk of becoming targets for disseminating information that can damage their reputation and welfare. This is included in the Information and Electronic Transactions Law which plays an important role in providing legal protection for children who are involved in the digital world or become public figures. The ITE Law is a tool to protect children from various potential abuse or exploitation. The ITE Law protects against defamation and fake news, namely:

- (1) Article 27A: "Every person intentionally attacks the honor or good name of another person by making allegations about something, to make the matter known to the public in the form of Electronic Information and/or Electronic Documents carried out through an Electronic System.
- (2) Article 28 paragraph 3: every person deliberately disseminates Electronic Information and/or Electronic Documents which he knows contains false notifications that cause unrest in society.

The principles of child protection according to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection are as follows:

- (1) Non-discrimination, which means protection for all Indonesian children without distinction of ethnicity, religion, race, class, gender, ethnicity, culture and language, the child's legal status, and the child's mental or mental condition.

- (2) The best interests of the child, is an action involving children carried out by the government, society, legislative and judicial bodies, so the best interests of the child must be the main consideration.
- (3) The right to life, survival, and development, the most basic human rights of children which must be protected by the state, government, society, family, and parents.
- (4) Respect for children's opinions, respect for children, respect for children's rights to participate and express their opinions in decision-making, especially those concerning children's lives.

According to Teguh (2012) [12] special protection for children who are economically or sexually exploited includes:

- (1) Dissemination or socialization of the provisions of laws and regulations relating to the protection of children who are economically or sexually exploited.
- (2) Monitoring, reporting, and imposing sanctions.
- (3) Involvement of various government agencies, companies, trade unions, non-governmental organizations, communities, and society in eliminating economic or sexual exploitation of children. All elements of society must be involved to support children's growth and development. Children who have been economically exploited have the right to receive protection and these children must not be excluded or degraded.

4.2. Law Enforcement Against Perpetrators Who Force Children to Work As Public Figures

Law enforcement in this case aims to protect children's basic rights, maintain physical and psychological health, and avoid economic exploitation. This strict law provides a guarantee that children will be protected from treatment that is detrimental to their future simply for economic or entertainment purposes. The appearance of child artists (public figures) on television or the internet certainly takes up children's time, disrupting children's activities as individuals who have not yet reached adulthood biologically, but also as individuals who have rights and potential that need to be protected and developed.

In the case of children who work as public figures, this will disrupt the child's rest time, which will disrupt the child's physical development. Judging from mental and social development, children as public figures will lose out mentally and socially with their peers at school. They spend more time on filming locations with lots of adults than children their age. Moreover, during busy work hours, they do not have time to play like children, so their mental growth is less developed. In terms of education, many children who work as public figures have to miss school because they come home from filming late at night, or catch up on screen time. In the case of Little B, in Deddy Corbuzier's podcast: B said that his income was Rp. 30,000,000,000, which came from filming until the end of his career, is said to be unknown and his biological mother was only given 10 percent of the income, the rest was enjoyed by his father. In M's case, although he did not specifically reveal any exploitation in the form of abuse or illegal acts carried out against him. However, he once talked about the mental and physical toll he felt during his years working in the entertainment world, which often forced him to sacrifice many things, including time with family and personal development. Apart from that, although many see Marshanda as a successful child artist,

there are times when she feels that her life is being lived in a way that is unnatural for a child. This condition often affected her mental health, and Marshanda then talked about how she experienced depression and felt depressed at these times.

In this case, there have never been any sanctions against perpetrators who carry out economic exploitation in cases of employing children to become public figures. However, this is stated in the Legislative Regulations, namely in Child Protection Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection, which was last amended by Law Number 17 of 2016 concerning Determination of Law Number 1 of 2016 concerning the second amendment to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection Article 76i which states that every person places, allows, commits, or participating in, or participating in, the economic or/and sexual exploitation of children.” So every parent or anyone who carries out economic or sexual exploitation of children will receive fines and sanctions. This is contained in Article 88 of Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection which states that anyone who violates the provisions as intended in Article 76i, shall be punished with imprisonment for a maximum of 10 years and/or a maximum fine of IDR 200,000,000.00 (two hundred million rupiahs). The results of the research reported by Garry and Harefa (2023) show that the children of public figures often become the center of attention of the public and interested parties. A child of a public figure who participates in being employed as a public figure in carrying out his profession must be based on developing his interests and talents because if it is not based on developing his interests and talents then this is categorized as an act of exploitation which is identified by the existence of coercion to fulfill the interests of interested parties. Acts of exploitation of the children of public figures have become the concern of various parties, both nationally and internationally because they are still widespread in this modern era. Therefore, there is a role and function of the child protection agency, namely KPAI, which is very necessary in preventing and handling exploitation cases involving children of public figures. Furthermore, it was reported by Wirasmita and Nurmawati (2023) that child victims of acts of exploitation in the artist profession must receive protection from the state, government, society, and parents, who are responsible for safeguarding and maintaining these human rights by the obligations imposed by law. Legal protection for child victims from acts of exploitation in the artist profession is regulated in the provisions of Article 66, Article 78, and Article 88 of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

- (1) Regarding legal protection for children, efforts to protect children's rights from acts of discrimination and exploitation in any form. Policies, efforts, and activities that ensure the realization of child protection can be interpreted as all efforts aimed at preventing, rehabilitating, and empowering children who experience acts of abuse, exploitation, and

neglect, to ensure the continuity of life and normal growth and development of children, both physically and mentally mental and social.

- (2) Efforts to prevent crime or opportunities for economic exploitation of children who do not receive justice for what has happened. Law enforcement is a bridge to provide firmness to perpetrators who cause trouble or discriminate against children in any way. As a protection for children's rights that must be fought for.

5.2. Suggestion

- (1) Parents should think more about those who choose to employ children. Must be aware of children's rights and ensure that their work in the entertainment world does not interfere with their education and welfare.
- (2) Tighten supervision of the entertainment industry and provide strict sanctions for those who violate it.
- (3) Providing psychological support and counseling services for children involved in the entertainment industry, to ensure children's mental and emotional well-being.

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